

Accretion efficiency and mass transfer in two binary star systems

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Abstract

We analyze the accretion properties of two binary star systems: the BY Draconis type variable V1803 Cyg, which is an A component of the binary system 61 Cyg and the semi-regular (SR) symbiotic variable NQ Gem. In this aim, we estimate an accretion efficiency in these binaries, based on the relation between luminosity and a rate of accretion. We give assumptions on the currently active mass transfer mechanism between the components in the binaries. This could be relevant to define the type of accretion, wind or disc is dominant for each of the objects. We compare the results for both objects, according to the features of their different stellar types. We appraise the possibilities for the transitions between the accretion regimes in the processes of evolution of the studied objects.

1 Introduction

The way the mass transfer is going through the components, defines its contribution level to the amplitudes of the brightness variability. The accretion flow is a product of interaction between the components in binary stars. The accretion mechanism gives possibilities to investigate the physical properties and conditions of astrophysical objects. The different accretion disc models could explain some peculiarities and variabilities in emissions, spectrum and brightness (Bell & Lin (1994)).

An estimation of accretion efficiency is important, because it has a close relation to the emitted energy and has a further role in binaries evolution. Its rate is different in different type of binary star objects and their stellar components. One advantage to know the accretion rate gives the possibility to estimate the mode of accretion and the possible transition between them.

For the purpose of this paper, we chose to study two objects, which are members of very different types: V1803 Cyg and NQ Gem. The first object, V1803 Cyg (hereafter 61 Cyg A) is a solar-type dwarf of spectral type K5 and it is a primary component of the visual binary 61 Cyg, which secondary component is a K7 dwarf 61 Cyg B. 61 Cyg A is an average active star (Duncan et al. (1991)) and its activity cycle was estimated as $\sim 7.35(\pm 0.1)yr$ (Baliunas et al. (1995)). This star was also defined with its solar-type variability (Hall et al. (2007); Lockwood et al. (2007)). During the seven years period a coronal activity (Robrade et al. (2012)) and a chromospheric cycle activity (Baliunas et al. (1995)) were detected. Both components of 61 Cyg are slow rotators and the periods of their rotation are: $\sim 35(\pm 1.7)$ days for the primary and $\sim 38(\pm 1.5)$ days for the secondary, respectively (Donahue et al. (1996); Saikia et al. (2016)). 61 Cyg A belongs to BY Draconis type variables (Kholopov et al. (1999)), which are emission-line dwarfs of dKe-dMe spectral type and they usually show quasiperiodic changes in the light curves. 61 Cyg A is also known as a strong X-ray source (Hempelmann et al. (2006); Robrade et al. (2012)).

The second object NQ Gem belongs to the family of Symbiotic variables of the Z Andromedae type. NQ Gem is classified as a suspected symbiotic star (catalogue of Belczyński et al. (2000)). Its SiIII/CIII ratio is similar to that of other symbiotic stars. The orbital period of NQ Gem is found to be 1308 days (Carquillat & Prieur (2008)), and its eccentricity is $e = 0.182$. The mass of the white dwarf or the object's primary star is close to a lower limit of $\sim 0.6M$. NQ Gem is a type of Semi-regular variables, which are giants or supergiants of intermediate and late spectral types. This star shows periodicity in its light curves variabilities, sometimes interrupted by various irregularities, possible to be detected for a long period of observations. These observational periods could prolong in the range from 20 to more than 2000 days. The object's brightness usually displays irregular variations and the amplitudes may vary with 1-2 mag, and its magnitude range is 7.4 – 8.18 in V. The light curves of NQ Gem manifest pulsations, with a pulsation period $P_{pul} \sim 58(\pm 1)d$ (Gromadzki et al. (2013)).

NQ Gem has also been attached to the group of X-Ray symbiotic binaries (Luna et al. (2013)). In the X-ray spectrum two components, at the soft part with energies below $\approx 1.5keV$ and at hard part above 2.5 keV, are clearly distinguished.

The aim in this paper is to define the differences in accretion processes. We discuss their effects on the accretion efficiency and accretion rate of the objects 61 Cyg A and NQ Gem. In Section 2, the basic formulas and the problem concepts are presented. The objects parameters and the results of calculations are given in Section 3. We analyse the obtained estimations of the results in Section 4. The mass transfer way is also a subject of the Discussion section.

2 Basic equations and concepts.

We use the next basic equations in order to calculate and estimate the accretion efficiency, accretion rate and parameters of the objects, such as: radii and temperature. The accretion efficiency η_{acc} is defined by the

expression:

$$\eta_{acc} = \frac{GM_1}{R_1 c^2}, \quad (1)$$

obtained by the expressions of accretion luminosity:

$$L_{acc} = \frac{GM_1 \dot{M}}{R_1} \text{ and } L_{acc} = \eta_{acc} \dot{M} c^2$$

Where M_1 and R_1 are the mass and radius of the central object or the primary star; G is the gravitational constant; c is the speed of light;

In general, the efficiency η expresses the amount of energy gained from the matter with mass m , in units of its mass energy (Kolb (2010)), usually obtained in percent of rest mass in the accretion process. Since the matter accumulating mechanism is not specified for our chosen objects, we can trace the change in efficiency in the three possible modes - disc accretion, spherical-like accretion and a two-stream feeding.

Equation 1 expresses the accretion efficiency in the presence of disc, or disc accretion. To obtain the expressions of the accretion efficiency in the other two modes, we will use the expressions of the accretion rates. The accretion efficiency is a useful measure that illustrates the power of accretion as an energy generator. It measures how the rest mass energy, per unit mass of the accreted material is converted into radiation.

If \dot{M} is the accretion rate in general case, \dot{M}_d expresses the disc accretion rate, by the equation, based on Frank et al. (2002):

$$\dot{M}_d = 2\pi R_{R1} \Sigma (-V_{acc}), \quad (2)$$

V_{acc} is the velocity of the stream, which in our case is equivalent to the radial velocity V_r . So, in the further calculations we will use the values of V_r . Σ is the surface density; R_{R1} the distance to the central object.

The spherical accretion rate could be expressed as (Bondi (1952); Edgar (2004)):

$$\dot{M}_{sph} = \pi R_{R1}^2 \rho (-V_{acc}), \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the volume density in this case.

If we denote the efficiency of the spherical accretion with ξ , then we can obtain its ratio to the efficiency of the disc accretion as a relation between two types of the accretion rates:

$$\frac{\xi}{\eta} = \frac{\dot{M}_d}{\dot{M}_{sph}}, \quad (4)$$

Then for the efficiency of the spherical accretion we can write:

$$\xi \approx \left(\frac{4H_d}{R_d}\right)\eta, \quad (5)$$

The last ratio (eq. 5) gives the relation between the two efficiency types. The whole disc radius R_d and the full half disc thickness H_d take part into the calculations. To consider the disc, the minimum value of H/R relation has to be $R = 10H$, for a thin disc it is $\sim R = 100H$. In our case, since we haven't specified the accretion mode in advance, we use an average approximation of this value $\sim R = 25H$.

The important relation between the luminosity L and the effective temperature T_{eff} is given by the application of Stefan-Boltzmann's law:

$$L = 4\pi R_{R1}^2 \sigma T_{eff}^4, \quad (6)$$

According to the different types of objects, we need to consider their physical properties. In the next section we will see whether and how this has an effect on the accretion efficiency values.

3 Systems parameters. Estimation of the accretion efficiency and accretion rate.

For the aim of this study, and following the equations in Section 2, we consider and apply next parameters of the two objects: Mass of the primary star $M_1 (M_\odot)$; Radius of the primary star $R_1 [R_\odot]$; Radial velocity V_r ; Mean values of Luminosity $L [L_\odot]$; Effective temperature $T_{eff} M_\odot$ and R_\odot are the mass and radius of the Sun.

For 61 Cyg A, we use the next parameters values: $R_1 \sim 0.665(\pm 0.005)R_\odot$ (Kervella et al. (2008)), $M_1 \sim 0.660M_\odot$ (Takeda et al. (2007)). The value of angular velocity Ω is evaluated as $\approx 17[km/s]$ (Hoffleit & Warren (1995)); V_r has the value $\sim -65.82km/s$ and $L [L_\odot]$ is $0.15L_\odot$; The calculations of the effective temperature T_{eff} give the values of 4374 K (Saikia et al. (2016)), 4450 K (Kervella et al. (2008)) to 4525 K (Takeda et al. (2007)). For the disc accretion rate of this object we obtain $\dot{M}_d \sim 1.6(\pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9} [M_\odot/yr]$.

For the second object, NQ Gem, we put the next values of the parameters into the calculations: $M_1 \sim 0.6M_\odot$ (Luna et al. (2013)); we calculated the distance from the central object at which the accretion rate reaches its maximum value as $R_M \sim 0.03R_\odot$; $V_r \sim 45.71km/s$; We apply the X-ray luminosity $L_x \sim 0.2L_\odot$ of NQ Gem (Luna et al. (2013)). We obtain the shock wave temperature T_{shw} , in the place with maximum accretion rate at R_M , $T_{shw} \sim 7.2(\pm 0.05) \times 10^4 K$. The disc accretion rate of NQ Gem reaches the value of $1.02 \times 10^{-8} [M_\odot/yr]$ (Luna et al. (2013)).

The set of parameters are listed in Table 1. The calculated errors are given in the table as well.

Further, to determine the accretion efficiency, we use the simple approach of these parameters into the equations, described in Section 2. The calculations give the evaluation of accretion efficiency for the two objects in the three suggested accretion modes: ξ for spherical accretion, η - for disc accretion, and a sum of both $\eta + \xi$ expresses the two-stream feed accretion. We refer 61 Cyg A as an Object C and NQ Gem as an Object G, using "C" and "G" as indexes of the quantities.

Then for the mean values of accretion efficiency, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_C &= 0.4(\pm 0.2) \times 10^{-4}; \\ \xi_G &= 0.2(\pm 0.2) \times 10^{-4}; \\ \eta_C &= 2.4(\pm 0.01) \times 10^{-4}; \\ \eta_G &= 1.28(\pm 0.12) \times 10^{-4}; \\ (\eta + \xi)_C &= 2.8(\pm 0.002) \times 10^{-4}; \\ (\eta + \xi)_G &= 1.5(\pm 0.14) \times 10^{-4}. \end{aligned}$$

The values of efficiency, as a result of our calculation are shown in table 2. For convenience, the three different accretion mode are presented by numbers, respectively: 1 - spherical accretion; 2 - disc accretion; 3 - two-stream supply accretion.

Based on the efficiency estimations of the three modes, We create an empirical figure (see Figure 1), from which we can indicate the variability of the efficiency during the transitions between the accretion modes.

Figure 1: The accretion efficiency growth $K[\%] \times 10^{-2}$ against the development of accretion modes A_{reg} .

As it was expected, the obtained accretion efficiency values differ for both objects: The values of the efficiency of both accretion modes of the Object C are approximately two times higher than that of the Object G. We observe that it increases smoothly at 61 Cyg A, while the increase in efficiency values at NQ Gem is steeper. This growth of efficiency is in accordance with the accretion mode development (A_{reg}) in order of increasing feed of an accreting matter. In the figure, the efficiency is presented in percent ($K[\%]$), multiplied by 10^{-2} .

4 Discussion.

4.1 Accretion efficiency of different accretion modes.

Here we discuss the difference in the results of the efficiency measurement of two objects. The objects are members of different types and it is supposed that they could have different physical properties. Since 61 Cyg A was defined as a slow rotator (Donahue et al. (1996); Saikia et al. (2016)), we could suggest that this allows to the accretion flow staying for a longer time in the object's gravitational field. Accordingly, an extraction of a larger accretion efficiency from the rest mass is possible to observe. This means further, a larger quantity of the rest mass is transformed in the form of a radiative energy. On the other hand, this has an effect on on the luminosity, which can lead to the larger efficiency. Then, the slow rotating accretor could give rise to smoothly increase of the efficiency. It is seen from the results that the reached values of 61 Cyg A efficiency are higher than those obtained for NQ Gem, at which the shape of this growth is sharper. From the objects' parameters description, we could evaluate the angular velocity of the Object C as $\sim 1/3$ of V_r , which in our opinion is high enough for the formation of an accretion ring to be very probable. If the disc is formed, it would be a short-lived formation.

4.2 Mass transfer properties.

After estimation of the accretion efficiency and the accretion rates, as well as the objects parameters (table 1), now we can discuss about what type of the mass transfer is dominant in each of the two objects.

The calculation and knowing of the mass transfer process could give an useful information of the interior of the donor and its evolution, as well as of the resulting properties of interacting area between the mass inflow and the primary star accretion zone (Solheim (2010)).

We could suppose about 61 Cyg A, It is possible of mass losing and matter scattering, realized by its approximately high accretion rate, but not very high accretion efficiency on the surface. From the results, related to the angular velocity values, we suppose unstable accretion structure. This way, an "A" component wind is also possible. Most likely a double feeding mass transfer could be observed: via wind and Roche Lobe Overflow.

As most symbiotic systems, NQ Gem is a binary in which a red giant transfers enough material to a compact companion. The ways of interaction between the companions could be different and depends on the system parameters. Although, it is common that the accretion mechanism in symbiotics is realized by wind accretion (Bondi & Hoyle (1944)), some considerations lead to the conclusion that accretion disc could be also formed in these systems (Livio & Warner (1984); Wynn (2008); Alexander et al. (2011)). On the other hand, an X-ray variability of NQ Gem in the range of $0.3 - 10 keV$, with a maximum count rates activity mostly in the hard band part of the energy spectrum, is detected, (see also Boneva (2018); Luna et al. (2013)). The NQ Gem X-ray luminosity could be contributed by the mass transfer via stellar wind.

5 Conclusion.

The objects parameters of the binary systems 61 Cyg A and NQ Gem are calculated. The disc accretion rates and the spherical accretion rates are evaluated. We estimated of how the average efficiency changes against the three suggested modes of accretion: disc accretion, spherical accretion and two-stream matter feeding. We found that the measured values of efficiency increase in order of the accretion modes development, in both objects in different ways. Smoothly increase with approximately two times higher values of the common efficiency in 61 Cyg A is observed; Sharp increase and lower efficiency values in NQ Gem. We can conclude that the mass transfer is highly possible to be realized by both at the same time via wind and Roche Lobe Overflow with irregular change of the accretion regime in K5 star 61 Cyg A For both objects we can say, they have the approximately high accretion rate, but not very high accretion efficiency.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the grant: Binary stars with compact objects, KII-06-H28/2 08.12.2018 (Bulgarian National Science Fund).

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Table 1: The basic parameters of two binary stars 61 Cyg A and NQ Gem, as follows: M_1 and R_1 are the mass and radius of the primary components; V_r is the radial velocity; L - the luminosity of 61 Cyg A; the X-ray luminosity value of NQ Gem is given in this column; T_{eff} is the effective temperature of 61 Cyg A and for NQ Gem we obtained the value T_{shw} , in the place with maximum accretion rate at R_M ; \dot{M}_d is the disc accretion rate. (The citations are given with numbers in brackets (see the footnote)):

¹[1]Kervella et al. (2008); [2]Halbwachs et al. (2018); [3]Saikia et al. (2016); [4]Luna et al. (2013); [5]this work.

Object	$M_1[M_\odot]$	$R_1[R_\odot]$	$V_r[km/s]$	$L[L_\odot]$	$T_{eff}[K]$	$\dot{M}_d[M_\odot/yr]$
61 Cyg A	0.69	0.665	-65.82	0.15	4450	$1.6(\pm 0.01) \times 10^{-9}$
Ref	[1]	[1]	[2]	[1,3]	[1,3]	[5]
NQ Gem	0.6	$0.03(\pm 10^{-4})$	45.71	0.20	$7.2(\pm 0.05) \times 10^4$	1.02×10^{-8}
Ref	[4]	[5]	[5]	[4]	[5]	[4]

Table 2: The mean values of accretion efficiency for the three different accretion modes, calculated for both objects.

Object Mode	1	2	3
$\times 10^{-4}$	ξ	η	$(\xi + \eta)$
Object C	0.4	2.4	2.8
Object G	0.2	1.28	1.5

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